

Hydrodynamic Modelling of a Two-Stage Biomass Gasification

Reactor

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Abstract

In our study the hydrodynamic behavior of a gasification reactor with two inlets and one outlet was numerically examined by the method of residence time distribution. We developed a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model of the reactor to solve the momentum and component balance equations of the system. The component balance equation was implemented to support the residence time distribution calculation. The mesh dependency of the CFD solution was checked by error rate and calculation time. In order to characterize the mixing and flow within reactor pulse experiments were performed numerically. A tracer impulse was introduced for 1 s to both inlets at the same time with concentration of 100 mol/m^3 approaching the Dirac delta function and tracer concentration at the outlet boundary of system was recorded. Compartmental modelling has a strong advantage over CFD as it has much smaller computational need. Therefore a compartment model in order to model the hydrodynamic structure of the reactor was also developed and compared to the results obtained by CFD model.

Keywords: Hydrodynamics, CFD simulation, Compartmental modelling, Tracer experiment, RTD analysis, Biomass gasification

1. Introduction

Biomass is an environment friendly resource as it consumes waste and turns them into energy or new valuable products. As fossil fuels tend to be exhausted, finding alternative energy sources is a popular and important research field. Nonhebel presented a method to estimate biomass yields in intensive and/or extensive production systems [1], and Lan et al. summarized the progress in techniques of biomass conversion into syngas

[2]. Bilandzia et al. studied the combustion properties of a species biomass aiming to gain electrical or heat energy [3]. Biomass is produced as a byproduct of many agricultural and industrial processes like harvesting and wood industry. There are two major groups of biomass, virgin and waste. They can be divided into subclasses i.e. terrestrial biomass, aquatic biomass as virgin biomass, municipal waste, agricultural solid waste, forestry residues and industrial wastes as waste biomass. Feedstock material for biomass reactors can be wood, straw, sawdust, rice husk, algae, water plant, leaves, black liquor, waste oil and so on [4]. The chemical composition of biomass is deeply depends on its type. The main material properties of interest, during subsequent processing as an energy source, relate to moisture content (intrinsic and extrinsic), calorific value, proportions of fixed carbon and volatiles, ash/residue content, alkali metal content and cellulose/lignin ratio [5]. Wood and woody biomass built up mainly from cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. These are formed of C, O and H, and N is organically bonded to them. Out of those three, cellulose is the main component which is a polysaccharide consisting D-glucose units. Hemicellulose is a complex polysaccharide mainly composed of pentose and hexose sugars, and lignin is a randomly linked, amorphous, high molecular weight phenolic compound [6]. In our laboratory-scale reactor cellulose was used as primary model component [7] for simplifying the chemical processes. Madenoglu et al. also studied biomass model compounds separately and mixed as well [8]. They gasified cellulose and lignin in a 100 mL batch reactor at 300, 400, 500 and 600 °C, and analyzed the gaseous, aqueous and residue products seeking for the highest H₂ and CH₄ yields.

Production of biofuels by green technologies gives an alternative to fossil fuels and for this reason biomass processing is an emerging topic in research and development. There are several options to convert biomass into energy and fuels. Biochemical routes include biological hydrogen production which has three main types i.e. fermentative hydrogen production, photosynthesis process and hydrogen production by biological water gas shift reaction. [9] All processes of biological hydrogen production are dependent on the presence of a hydrogen-producing enzyme, whose activity is dependent on proper temperature and pH. The biochemical process is very rigorous, long period, and hard for large-scale applications. [10] Another way to gain combustible energy source from biomass is the physico-chemical route in which the biomass is pretreated before combustion. Pretreatment can be performed by pelletization: raw biomass is converted into a pellet form with improved fuel quality such as increased bulk density, and uniformed shape and size. [11] This can be a pretreatment for thermochemical utilization, but also a form of utilization itself. Among biochemical, physico-chemical and thermochemical routes, thermochemical, the one with most potential and challenge, was chosen for further study. The main thermo-chemical processes include pyrolysis, combustion, gasification, hydrothermal liquefaction and

hydrothermal carbonization [6]. Out of these processes, pyrolysis and gasification can produce high quality syngas or liquid fuel efficiently [12], and will be discussed in this study.

Studies show that biomass thermochemical conversion like gasification under elevated temperature is essentially a complex process, which contains two often overlapping stages: biomass pyrolysis at relatively low temperature for release of volatiles [13], and volatile reforming or gasifying under elevated temperature [14]. When using a two-stage pyrolysis/gasification system, in which the upper stage is the biomass pyrolysis to release volatiles and the lower stage is the volatile gasification, it is much easier to study, simulate and predict gas production and proportion of gas components [15].

During gasification thermal degradation of carbonaceous material takes place in the presence of an externally supplied oxidizing agent. Air, oxygen and water steam are the most common agents, each having different advantages. Air causes more nitrogen oxides which highly affect the heating characteristics of the final product. Oxygen has also been reported as an ideal gasifying agent but is not good for producing fuel gas or chemical byproducts. While steam can play not only the role of oxidizing agent, it also can help in the gas reforming process [16]. In our equipment steam was used as gasifying agent. Catalyst plays an important role in gasification and is used to help the process getting through the energy barrier. In our two-stage fixed-bed reaction system a Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst was used.

Although the experiments can reveal some reaction mechanism and we can choose the appropriate reaction parameters according to experimental results, the reaction processing especially hydrodynamic behavior is still unknown, which is important for equipment reactor designing. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is a widely used tool for modelling and simulating the behavior of reactors. Gómez-Barea and Leckner [17] as well as Sharma, Pareek and Zhang [18] discussed the usability of CFD models for investigation of biomass gasification reactors. Computer simulation allows analyzing and optimizing the behavior of a real system without influencing it physically. Commercial and open source CFD codes are available for calculating the flow equations in equipment. The whole process of CFD simulation can be divided into five parts. Firstly the geometry of the problem is defined. Secondly the whole geometry is divided into smaller elements creating the calculation mesh. In the third part the appropriate flow equations, their parameters and the boundary conditions are specified. In the fourth part the problem is solved by a selected numerical method on the calculation mesh. Finally the results of calculations are visualized. The accuracy of the CFD solution is strongly depended on the mesh quality while the computational time increases with the number of mesh elements. When the accuracy is not changing significantly with the increasing number of mesh elements the calculation can be considered mesh independent.

CFD has high computational need, but information technology improves quickly. Increasing the number of processor cores, the memory and clock speed, the calculations can be completed in reasonable time. Parallel computing is also a promising way to speed up the numerical calculations [19].

Residence time refers to the time the material flowing through an equipment. The concept of residence time distribution (RTD) was first introduced by Danckwerts [20]. He studied the flow and mixing of fluids in non-ideal tubes, mixers and reactors. There are many examples in the literature in which RTD is used in the hydrodynamic study of equipment. In the research of Gamba et al. [21] a stirred tank was examined by RTD. They simulated the hydrodynamics of the reactor by CFD software and validated the results of tracer method by experimental data and literature information. Adeosun and Lawal carried out a numerical and experimental studies on mixing characteristics in a T-junction microchannel using residence time distribution [22]. They also applied pulse tracer experiments. They calculated the moments of the RTD and coefficient of variation to quantify the mixing behavior. The RTD is obtained commonly by injecting a tracer instantaneously (pulse input) or at a constant rate (step input) at the inlet of a flow system, and then measuring the tracer concentration at the outlet as a function of time. RTD analysis can be simulated by CFD solving the stationary momentum balance equation and then dealing with the time-dependent component balance using the previously calculated velocity field.

Compartment models also can be used to describe the hydrodynamic structure of complex systems using a set of elements of ideal reactor models, mixers and distributors. The main advantage of compartment model is that it requires less computation capacity compared to CFD simulations. Egedy et al. modelled a stirred system by both compartment model and CFD model [23]. Compartment models are used for modelling biological systems (e.g. fermenters) [24], modelling aired systems [25] and optimization tasks [26]. Kong et al. researched the application of compartment models in case of gasification reactors [27]. In our work we defined a simple compartmental model to model the gasification reactor by applying a sequence of plug-flow reactors, continuous stirred-tank reactors and a mixer. The results of the compartmental model were compared to the results of CFD model constructed previously. MATLAB software was used for data processing and compartmental modelling; furthermore COMSOL Multiphysics software package was used for CFD modelling.

2. Materials and methods

In this study, a laboratory-scale two-step reactor with downdraft operation and fixed-bed catalyst is modelled. The details of the reaction system could be seen in our previous work [7]. Figure 1 shows the reactor with the location of the two inlets and one outlet. Nitrogen is introduced by volume flow rate $9.16 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ on the side

of the top of the reactor. Feedstock (which is cellulose microcrystalline powders of 20 μm particle size purchased from Sigma–Aldrich Co., Ltd.) is placed in a container signed as cellulose boat in Figure 1. The pyrolysis step takes place in the first half of the reactor. The gasifying agent water steam is introduced to the gasification section through an immersed tube by volume flow rate of $8.15 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. Water steam reacts with the products of pyrolysis as it exits the immersed tube at the beginning of gasification section. The gasification takes place in the second half of the reactor. The reactor temperature is 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the whole geometry, according to the experimental study. Ni/ Al_2O_3 catalyst with 15 w/w % of Ni is layered in a fixed-bed section. The chemical compounds do not modify our model since we focus only on hydrodynamics in this work. The composition of the gas exiting the reactor is controlled by the volume flow rate of steam [7].

Figure 1. The schematic diagram of the gasification reactor.

CFD methods use partial differential equations to describe and solve time-spatial flow problems for a given geometry. In our case, the gasification reactor shown in Figure 1 was modelled and simulated by CFD. The flow field was calculated by a single phase laminar flow model using the momentum (Eq 1) and the continuity (Eq 2) equations.

$$\rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot [-p\mathbf{I} + \mu(\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T) - \frac{2}{3}\mu(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u})\mathbf{I}] + \mathbf{F} \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

where ρ is density, \mathbf{u} is velocity, p is pressure, μ is dynamic viscosity and \mathbf{F} are external forces. Using of laminar flow is appropriate here since the Reynolds number is profusely under the limit of turbulence. The volume flow of steam and nitrogen were defined as boundary conditions at the inlets. The outlet was defined as a pressure boundary. All the other boundaries were treated as no momentum flux walls.

In this numerical study we characterized the hydrodynamic behavior of gasification reactor using residence time distribution analysis based on CFD simulation. For this reason, we completed the Navier-Stokes equation with the component model given by the equation below (Eq 3).

$$\nabla \cdot (-D_i \nabla c_i) + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla c_i = R_i \quad (3)$$

where D_i is the diffusion coefficient for component i , ∇c_i is the concentration gradient of component i , and R_i is source term for component i . In our simulation the source term R was set to 0. However it can be replaced by the chemical reaction or other sources in the future applications. For the components the wall boundaries are defined as no component flux boundaries. To simulating a tracer pulse experiment, we introduced a tracer impulse for 1 s to both inlets at the same time with concentration of 100 mol/m³ and solved the component balance equation transiently.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Mesh independence study

In the mesh independence study, we defined the 3D geometry of the reactor in the CFD software and generated a calculation mesh with different qualities. A predefined mesh with 11.9 mm, 7.74 mm and 5.96 mm maximum element size was applied. In the case of mass balance, an increasing number of elements caused decreasing error rate but also increased the calculation time (Figure 2.a). Calculations are performed on a Dell Optiplex 790 PC with 16 GB memory.

Figure 2. Effect of number of mesh elements on solution time and error rate in case of a) mass balance and b) component balance.

In the case of component balance similar correlation can be seen as Figure 2.b shows. Error rate is calculated as the absolute value of the difference between the cumulate inlet and outlet component mass divided by the cumulate inlet component mass in percent. The mesh independence results show that applying higher mesh quality significantly decreases the error rate but increases the computational time. For the subsequent simulations, we selected the finest mesh because it provides the best result in accuracy with reasonable calculation time. The total number of mesh elements applied was 220121. Some details of the calculation mesh are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The calculation mesh of gasification reactor. a) whole geometry, b) Inlet 1, c) Inlet 2, d) Outlet.

3.2. Flow field calculations by CFD

In the numerical study the stationary solution of gasification reactor was first calculated. The velocity field obtained by solving the momentum balance equation is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Velocity field contours of gasification reactor [m/s] calculated at different mass flow rates of water steam. a) 0.01 g/min b) 0.02 g/min c) 0.05 g/min d) 0.1 g/min e) 0.2 g/min

Streamline plots are generally used to visualize the directions of flow. In Figure 5 the streamlines of different sections of the reactor are highlighted.

Figure 5. Streamlines in the gasification reactor in case of 0.1 g/min flow rate of water steam. a) Inlet 1, b) Inlet 2, c) Outlet.

3.3. Residence time distribution analysis

Using the previously calculated stationary velocity field of the reactor, we performed a pulse experiment by application of tracer material in time to both inlets approaching a Dirac delta function. The tracer injection was applied as a rectangle function with concentration of 100 mol/m^3 for 1 s long duration. In Figure 6.a the black dotted line shows the concentration curve of the system detected at the outlet boundary. The red line represents the case when the tracer material is applied only to Inlet 1, and the green line represents the case when the tracer material is applied only to Inlet 2. As it is shown by the initial narrow peak section of the residence time distribution the trace material originated from Inlet 2 reaches the outlet earlier. The concentration profiles of the reactor at four different times (13 s, 18 s, 73 s, 260 s) are also inserted in Figure 6.a.

Figure 6. Residence time distribution of the system. a) Inflows effect on concentration at the outlet. b) Effect of varying water steam inflow rate on outlet concentration.

The H₂ yield of gasification reactor can be controlled by steam feed while keeping nitrogen feed constant [7]. Figure 6.b shows the change of the tracer concentration at outlet boundary at different values of the steam flow rate. The maximum value of the first concentration peak increases by incrementing the inflow rate of steam. In the latter section of concentration curve, the tracer concentration tends to get higher values as the steam flow rate decreases. The value of average residence time was calculated from residence time distribution for each value of steam flow (Table 1). It can be seen from the values of Table 1 that average residence time increases as the steam flow rate decreases.

Table 1. Average residence time at different flow rates of the gasifying agent (Inlet 2).

Total volume (V)	Volume flow rate of Inlet 1	Mass flow rate of Inlet 2	Volume flow rate of Inlet 2	Average residence time
[m ³]	[m ³ /s]	[g/min]	[m ³ /s]	[s]
1.02E-03	9.16E-06	0.01	8.15E-07	102.06
		0.02	1.63E-06	95.17
		0.05	4.07E-06	79.19
		0.1	8.15E-06	64.00
		0.2	1.63E-05	43.83

3.4. Compartment model

A system could be described by a sequence of compartments such as plug-flow reactor (PFR), continuous stirred-tank or perfectly mixed reactor (PMR), mixer (M) and distributor (D) [28]. It was supposed that mixers and distributors have no volumes in the compartment model of the gasification reactor. Equation 4 and 5 describe the model of the PMR compartment.

$$F_{out} = F_{in} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = \frac{F_{in}}{V} (c_{a,in} - c_a) \quad (5)$$

where F_{out} is the flow rate of the outlet, F_{in} is the flow rate of the inlet, c_a is the actual concentration of component a , $c_{a,in}$ is the inlet concentration of component a and V is the total volume of the reactor. The PFR is approximated by consecutive PMR compartments giving the characteristics of plug-flow. Connection of compartments is described by an incidence matrix where -1 is the sign for an outgoing stream, 1 is the sign for incoming stream and 0 shows that neither outgoing nor incoming stream occurs. Following the structure of the physically implemented gasification reactor we constructed a compartment model which can be seen in Figure 7. The connection of applied compartments is described by incidence matrix shown in Table 2. The pyrolysis section of reactor is replaced by a PFR. A mixer is applied at the end of immersed tube to introduce the water steam into the mean flow. The catalyst bed was modelled by a PMR, and the remained reactor sections are considered as PFRs.

Figure 7. Compartment model of the reactor consisting of unites u_1 – u_5 and streams s_1 – s_7 .

Table 2. Incidence matrix of the constructed compartment model.

	u_1 (PFR)	u_2 (Mixer)	u_3 (PFR)	u_4 (PMR)	u_5 (PFR)
s_1 (Inlet 1)	1	0	0	0	0
s_2	-1	1	0	0	0
s_3 (Inlet 2)	0	1	0	0	0
s_4	0	-1	1	0	0
s_5	0	0	-1	1	0
s_6	0	0	0	-1	1
s_7 (Outlet)	0	0	0	0	-1

The proportion of compartments volumes applied in calculations was set to 53.26%, 22%, 0.28%, 24.46% according to the volume of the four main real section of the reactor (Figure 7). In the case of compartment model, the ideal plug-flow reactors are approximated by a cascade of continuous perfectly mixed reactors. The number of PMRs in PFR can be an adjustable parameter of compartment models. In our calculations, the number of PMR that used to approximate PFR was set to 10 because we found that increasing the cascade number above 10 does not result better approximation. The time step of calculation was fixed 0.2 seconds as we used simple explicit Euler method to solve the differential equation. Figure 8.a shows the comparison of concentration curves obtained by the CFD and compartment model. Good agreement can be seen between the results calculated by the

CFD model and the much simpler compartment model. We calculated an absolute and a squared error to characterize the difference between the results by the two models.

As an experiment, the volume of compartments was determined by applying an optimization tool (Particle Swarm Optimization [29], MATLAB) that uses the objective function given by Equation 6.

$$\min \sum (c_{\text{compartment model}}(t) - c_{\text{CFD}}(t))^2 \quad (6)$$

The objective function calculates the sum of differences of concentration values calculated by CFD and the compartment model in every second. Figure 8.b shows the comparison of concentration curves obtained by the CFD and the optimized compartment model.

Figure 8. Residence time distributions obtained by CFD and compartment model. a) volume of compartments are determined from the real reactor structure; b) volume of compartments are obtained by using optimization algorithm.

The results obtained by the two approaches are summarized in Table 3. The absolute and squared errors were found significantly smaller in the case of optimized compartment model, but remarkable differences are obtained in the volume proportion of plug-flow reactor u_3 and u_5 (reactor sections before and after catalyst bed in the gasification section), and perfectly mixed reactor u_4 (catalyst bed). The volume proportion of reactor sections in the two cases are also shown in Figure 9. Because of the volume proportions proposed by the optimization tool differ significantly from the real reactor volume structure. Thus the further use of these results is not considered.

Table 3. Compartment model parameters and simulation results.

	Real volume ratio of compartments	Optimized volume ratio of compartments
Number of cascade element in PFR model (N)	10	10
Time step	0.2 s	0.2 s
Absolute error	46.45	33.40
Squared error	27.96	10.69
Volume proportion of u_1	53.26%	54.53%
Volume proportion of u_3	22%	16.58%
Volume proportion of u_4	0.28%	12.3%
Volume proportion of u_5	24.46%	16.58%

Figure 9. Volume proportion values of compartment elements in the case of two approaches 1.) volumes are given by the real reactor structure; 2.) volumes given by the optimization tool.

Figure 10 shows the residence time distributions in the cases when the steam flow rate was set to 0.01 g/min, 0.02 g/min, 0.05 g/min and 0.2 g/min. In all cases, the results of the compartment model calculated with the volume proportions of real reactor structure fit well with the results of CFD simulation. The simulation parameters and the calculated differences are collected in Table 4.

Figure 10. Residence time distributions of the gasification reactor obtained by CFD and compartment model at different steam flow rate: a) 0.01 g/min, b) 0.02 g/min, c) 0.05 g/min and d) 0.2 g/min.

Table 4. Simulation parameters and error values.

Number of cascade element in PFR model (N)	10			
time step	0.2 s			
F_{steam} (s₃)	0.01 g/min	0.02 g/min	0.05 g/min	0.2 g/min
absolute error	45.19	43.76	40.80	42.14
squared error	17.59	15.38	14.44	36.67
Volume proportion of u₁	53.26%			
Volume proportion of u₃	22%			
Volume proportion of u₄	0.28%			
Volume proportion of u₅	24.46%			

4. Conclusions

A gasification reactor was examined in hydrodynamic point of view. The momentum and component balances of the reactor with prescribed geometry and operation parameters were solved by a CFD software. A residence time distribution analysis was performed to characterize the hydrodynamics of the reactor based on results calculated by the CFD model. In addition to CFD modelling, we approximated the system with a compartmental model built up from ideal reactor models and a mixer. The proportion of compartments volumes were determined by calculating the volume of the real reactor structure for the particular sections. The concentration values at the outlet were calculated and compared to the results obtained from the more sophisticated CFD model and good agreement was found. In the numerical experiments, we investigated the effect of different feeding rates of gasification agent. As an experiment, an optimization tool was used to determine the optimal volumes of the compartments aiming a better agreement with the CFD result. Due to the optimization technique, we got smaller differences, although the volume structure of reactor changed considerably. Thus the further use of the results of optimization method is not considered. According to the results of this study, the model set-up together with the applied simulation methods proved to be a useful tool for the hydrodynamic analysis of gasification reactor.

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